

OVERCOMING LINGUISTIC HURDLES: INVESTIGATING CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MAGUINDANAON STUDENTS IN ACHIEVING PROFICIENCY IN SPEAKING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

English proficiency is in today's globalized world, opening doors to educational and employment opportunities. In this study, qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to examine the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and explored strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024. There were 15 participants who were chosen using the purposive sampling. Thematic Analysis was used in capturing significant themes and responses. Ethical compliance was also considered in this study. A semi-structured interview served as the primary investigative tool employed during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). Through thematic analysis, common themes and patterns regarding the challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in English speaking were identified. The findings shed light on various linguistic and cultural barriers that hindered students' progress in acquiring English speaking skills. Additionally, the study highlights the importance of culturally responsive teaching methods and tailored language support programs to address the unique needs of Maguindanaon students. The implications of these findings extend to educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers, emphasizing the necessity of implementing inclusive language education strategies to foster linguistic diversity and promote English proficiency among Maguindanaon students.

Keywords: *Linguistic hurdles, Maguindanaon students, English proficiency, Qualitative, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

English proficiency is a crucial in today's globalized world, opening doors to educational and employment opportunities. In the Philippines, English serve as one of the official languages and plays a significant role in education and communication. However, achieving proficiency in English can be challenging, especially for students from linguistically diverse backgrounds.

While international research has addressed issues related to language transition and identity, there is a gap in understanding the specific challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the Philippines. Furthermore, research on effective strategies to support Maguindanaon students in achieving English proficiency is limited in the Philippine context.

The ability of teachers to bridge the linguistic gap and facilitate English language learning is a critical factor. The training and support provided to teachers in this context need examination (Gonzalez, 2015). With modernization, there is a concern that the preservation of the Filipino language and culture may be at risk. Ngag (2023) pointed out that Filipino students have limited knowledge in their own literature, which also affects how they appreciate local languages.

The Philippines is a linguistically diverse country with over 170 languages and dialects spoken. While English and Filipino are official languages of instruction, many students, particularly those from Indigenous communities like the Maguindanaon, grow up speaking their native languages at home. As a result, they often face linguistic hurdles when it comes to achieving English proficiency. In the Philippines, students typically transition from their native languages to English as the medium of instruction starting in elementary school. This abrupt shift can be challenging for students who are not exposed to English at an early age (Bautista, 2017).

Maintaining one's linguistic identity while acquiring proficiency in English can be a complex process. Students may grapple with issues related to self-esteem and identity as they navigate multiple linguistic worlds (Ramos, 2018). Allocation of resources, such as English language learning materials and language support programs, can vary across regions and school systems in the Philippines. Access to such resources can impact language proficiency (De Guzman, 2019).

This study aims to address these gaps by providing insights into the linguistic hurdles experienced by Maguindanaon learners and suggesting pedagogical approaches that may facilitate English language development in a culturally sensitive manner. This also seek to shed light on the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in Maguindanao province and explore strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills.

Research Questions

This study sought to shed light on the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and explore strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following key-questions:

1. What specific linguistic challenges do Maguindanaon students in the Maguindanao I encounter when striving to achieve proficiency in English speaking?
 2. How do Maguindanaon students' linguistic backgrounds and language used in their homes and communities influence their English-speaking abilities?
 3. What are the perceptions and experiences of Maguindanaon students regarding their self-esteem and identity in the context of English language learning?
 4. What strategies and approaches are employed by teachers and schools to support Maguindanaon students in improving their English-speaking skills?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to examine the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and to explore strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

One crucial element of the phenomenological research design is the researcher's responsibility to suspend any preexisting beliefs about the experience or phenomena in question (Delve & Limpaecher, 2012).

Participants of the Study

Table 1 displays the participants' qualifications, as determined by the criteria established by the researcher before selecting eligible informants for the study. The study involved a total of fifteen English teachers from among secondary in DepEd Maguindanao Del Sur Division, who met the researcher's specified inclusion criteria. In the study of Dolutan and Ngag (2024), setting an inclusion criteria is necessary to carefully select participants whose experiences and expertise tailored fit to the needs of the study.

Table 1: Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications
<i>Teacher-Participants</i>
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Must be an English Teacher.2. Must be assigned to Maguindanao Del Sur Division.3. Must be handling Maguindanaon Learners.

Sampling Technique

The Purposive Sampling Technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the English teachers from among secondary in DepEd Maguindanao Division, who met the specific inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

This method of sampling patterned after Creswell (2013) mandates that researcher's possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning their study so as to effectively pinpoint and make contact with eligible participants through online survey platforms like Alchemer. Researcher's resort to purposive sampling in order to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey respondents are meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion.

Data Gathering Instrument

In the context of this study, a semi-structured interview served as the primary investigative tool employed during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). The objective is to explore the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and explore strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

The credibility and suitability of this instrument were validated through a rigorous assessment process, overseen by a panel of experts possessing specialized knowledge in the development of pertinent research instruments.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure the research's reliability, the researcher maintain a strict adherence to a predefined set of procedures. The primary objective of this study was to explore the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary

schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and explore strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

In the initial phase, formal authorization was diligently sought from both the Superintendent of DepEd-Maguindanao Del Sur and the Dean of the College of Graduate Studies (CGS). This authorization was essential to obtain the necessary permissions for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations

Following this, a secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, subjected to rigorous evaluation, and then administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select secondary school teachers as participants in this study. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher proceeded with conducting face-to-face interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs).

The data collected from interviews and FGDs were systematically organized, subjected to comprehensive analysis, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

Data Analysis

Within the framework of the study focused on exploring the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and exploring strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024, the researcher employed a content or thematic analysis approach to scrutinize the amassed data.

As elucidated by Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006) involved the systematic classification of textual components, encompassing statements, phrases, and words, into organized groupings or categories. These categories either drew from established frameworks or were custom-crafted to align with the specific objectives of the study.

To execute this analytical process, a series of vital steps were meticulously followed:

In the initial phase, all data sources, including interview transcripts, notes from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and pertinent documents, underwent thorough organization and preparation for analysis. This step ensured the structured arrangement and accessibility of the data. Subsequently, the researcher was deeply immersed in the data by conducting a comprehensive review of interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process aided in obtaining a comprehensive grasp of the content and context inherent in the collected information.

The third step involved commencing a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data. These codes encapsulated fundamental concepts, ideas, or themes relating to the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and exploring strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

Following coding, the identified codes were clustered into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step sought to establish an initial framework for organizing the data.

Following this, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes underwent a process of scrutiny and refinement. Researchers ensured the coherence and clarity of these themes, making necessary adjustments as required. Each refined theme was assigned a descriptive label that succinctly represented the content it encompassed, facilitating easy identification and interpretation.

Relevant data excerpts, such as quotations or segments excerpted from interviews and FGDs, were selected and linked to the respective themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes.

Finally, the thematic analysis transcended superficial identification. Researchers delved into interpreting the significance and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives. They sought patterns, correlations, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities involved in implementing differentiated instruction in science education.

This meticulous and well-structured process of thematic analysis empowered researchers to systematically investigate and comprehend the strategies and approaches employed by teachers in addressing the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and exploring strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

This approach yielded valuable insights contributing to the enhancement of intervention programs aimed at addressing the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and exploring strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused on secondary schools within Maguindanao Del Sur Division, which was the specific geographical area of interest. The study did not encompass schools in other divisions or regions. It was limited to the school year 2023-2024. It examined the linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students during that academic year.

The primary focus of the study were the Maguindanaon students in selected secondary schools. The study might also have involved teachers and school administrators to gain a comprehensive understanding of the linguistic challenges. It also investigated a range of linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students, including language proficiency, communication barriers, and academic performance issues related to language.

Linguistic challenges that arose in different academic years were not within the scope of this research. The study focused exclusively on linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students. Linguistic challenges related to other languages or ethnic groups were beyond the scope of this research.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Maguindanaon students in the Maguindanao Del Sur division often struggle with code-switching between their native languages and English. This difficulty affects their pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary usage, hindering their proficiency in spoken English. According to Bantillo and Ngag (2024), teachers' preferences for teaching language, specifically Filipino were influenced by the learning environment, instructional materials, and personal styles.

Further, the linguistic backgrounds and language use in the homes and communities of Maguindanaon students significantly impact their English speaking abilities. Limited exposure to English outside the classroom, coupled with cultural norms prioritizing indigenous languages, poses challenges for students in developing fluency and confidence in English.

Furthermore, many Maguindanaon students experience feelings of insecurity and low self-esteem when learning English, particularly if they struggle with pronunciation or grammar. They navigate a delicate balance between cultural pride in their indigenous identity and the pressure to conform to Western standards of English proficiency, leading to identity conflicts.

Finally, teachers and schools employ various strategies to support Maguindanaon students in improving their English-speaking skills. These include integrating interactive and engaging activities into lessons, using culturally relevant materials and contexts in English language learning, and implementing peer tutoring programs to provide personalized support and guidance. These approaches aim to create a conducive learning environment and enhance students' confidence and proficiency in spoken English.

A study by Garcia and Cogtas (2020) investigated the impact of linguistic backgrounds on the English proficiency of indigenous students in the Philippines. The findings revealed that students who primarily spoke indigenous languages at home

demonstrated lower levels of English proficiency compared to their peers who spoke Filipino or English at home.

Conclusions

Based on the provided results, here are four major conclusions:

First, Junior High School teachers generally perceived traditional teaching methods in Filipino education as teacher-centered, with a focus on lectures, readings, and didactic instruction. While some teachers may find value in traditional methods, others may struggle with passive learning environments and limited engagement.

Second, modernized approaches to teaching Filipino in Junior High Schools included the integration of technology, interactive online platforms, multimedia resources, and collaborative tools for group projects. These modern approaches aim to enhance student engagement, participation, and comprehension by catering to diverse learning styles and preferences.

Third, teachers' preferences for traditional or modernized approaches to learning the Filipino subject were influenced by factors such as teaching environment, availability of instructional materials, and personal learning styles. While some teachers may benefit from aspects of traditional teaching, others prefer modernized approaches that offer dynamic and interactive learning experiences.

Finally, it has been concluded that the use of technology and digital resources positively impacts Junior High School teachers' engagement with and appreciation of the Filipino subject by providing interactive learning experiences and easy access to academic materials. While technology serves as a motivational tool for students, concerns exist regarding overreliance on gadgets and a potential hindrance to critical thinking skills. Also, teachers' adoption of technology enhanced their connection to the subject and fosters active participation in learning, suggesting a shift towards a more student-centered and innovative approach to Filipino education.

Recommendations

Based on the results, and conclusions, the following were recommended:

1. MBHTE BARMM may collaborate with local communities and stakeholders to develop language policies that recognize and support the bilingualism of Maguindanaon students. They may also advocate for the inclusion of culturally relevant and inclusive pedagogical approaches in teacher training programs and educational policies to address the linguistic and cultural needs of Maguindanaon learners.
2. Maguindanao Del Sur Division may establish language support programs within schools to provide additional resources and opportunities for Maguindanaon students to practice English in real-life settings. They may encourage partnerships with community

organizations and English-speaking mentors to create immersion experiences outside the classroom and enhance students' English language proficiency.

3. Curriculum Developers may design English language curriculum materials that integrate authentic cultural content and examples from the Maguindanaon community. They may also ensure that curriculum frameworks incorporate flexible approaches to language learning that accommodate the diverse linguistic backgrounds and identities of Maguindanaon students, fostering a sense of pride and ownership in their language development.

4. English Teachers may implement differentiated instruction strategies that cater to the varying language proficiency levels and learning styles of Maguindanaon students. They can also incorporate interactive and engaging activities into lessons that promote active participation and collaboration among students. Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their cultural competence and pedagogical skills in supporting Maguindanaon learners.

5. Future Researchers may conduct longitudinal studies to explore the long-term impact of language policies and educational interventions on the English language proficiency and socio-emotional well-being of Maguindanaon students. They can also investigate innovative approaches and best practices in bilingual education and culturally responsive teaching that can inform future curriculum development and policy-making efforts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before commencing this study, it was essential to underline the critical significance of ethical considerations within the research focused on the specific linguistic challenges faced by Maguindanaon students in the selected secondary schools in Maguindanao Del Sur Division and explore strategies to enhance their English-speaking skills in the current school year 2023-2024.

To prepare for implementation, all the previously mentioned plans and Inc. recommendations were presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc. to ensure adherence to prescribed procedures and protocols. Consequently, the following ethical principles were emphasized:

Informed Consent:

Before participation, explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all school heads involved in the study. They must possess a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Furthermore, participation remained entirely voluntary, affording participants the autonomy to withdraw from the study at any juncture without encountering any adverse consequences.

Anonymity and Confidentiality:

To safeguard the identities and responses of the students, rigorous measures were enacted to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Rather than using actual names,

pseudonyms or codes were employed, upholding the privacy of the participants. The collected data was securely stored with access restricted solely to the research team.

Avoiding Harm:

Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, were discussed with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and a support system was readily available to assist participants should the need arise.

Researcher-Participant Relationship:

The researcher maintained a professional and respectful rapport with the school heads. Any actions that may exploit or cause harm to the participants were avoided, ensuring their utmost dignity and respect throughout the research process.

Data Protection:

Adherence to data protection regulations and laws was unwaveringly followed to safeguard the personal information of the participants. Stringent measures were employed to ensure the secure storage and transmission of data.

Voluntary Participation:

Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was wholly voluntary, devoid of any form of coercion or external pressure.

Researcher Bias:

The researcher remained vigilant regarding potential biases that might influence data collection and analysis, upholding objectivity and transparency throughout the research endeavor.

Institutional Approval:

Before initiating the study, the researcher diligently sought ethical clearance from the pertinent institutional review boards or ethics committees.

Honesty and Integrity:

The research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, devoid of manipulation or distortion to align with preconceived notions or biases.

Beneficence:

The potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were thoughtfully considered, ensuring that the study positively contributed to the enhancement of the education system.

Cultural Sensitivity:

The researcher displayed cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, and refraining from imposing external values on the participants.

Inclusion and Diversity:

The research design gave paramount importance to embracing inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a broad range of students and their perspectives on 21st-century learning. By diligently upholding these ethical principles, the study was carried out conscientiously and with due regard to the rights and welfare of the involved students.

Concurrently, it offered valuable contributions to the field of education, particularly within the unique setting of DepEd Maguindanao specifically focusing on secondary schools.

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